

Moberg Flap in the Reconstruction of Allen Type III Thumb Tip Injuries: A Case Report

Gabriel Alcalá-Soto^{*1}, Luis Enrique Hernández-Alcalá², Yuliet Guadalupe Sánchez-Javier³, Rafael Mendez-Reynosa⁴, Irad Antonio Zúñiga-Salazar⁵, Felipe Alarcón-Estrada⁶, Jose Alfonso Simental-Andrade⁷, Miguel Ángel Zozaya-Niño⁸, Kevin Adrian Tinajero-Camacho⁹, Andrea Alvarado-Herrera¹⁰, Alejandro Herbert Oliva-Arvizu¹¹

¹Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery Resident, "Adolfo López Mateos" Medical Center, ISEM

²Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

³General Surgery Resident, Hospital General Regional No. 1 IMSS, Querétaro

⁴Universidad Anáhuac México

⁵General Surgery Resident, Hospital General Regional No. 251 IMSS

⁶Universidad Anáhuac México

⁷General Surgery Resident, Hospital general de zona No. 6, IMSS, Nuevo León

⁸Universidad de Durango

⁹General Surgery Resident, Hospital de Especialidades Centro Médico Nacional Siglo XXI, IMSS

¹⁰Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México

¹¹General Surgery Resident, Hospital General Regional No. 1 IMSS, Querétaro

ABSTRACT

Background: Thumb tip injuries involving soft tissue loss and bone exposure represent a reconstructive challenge due to the need to preserve digital length, restore sensibility, and maintain pinch function. The Moberg flap (bilateral volar neurovascular advancement flap) is a classic reconstructive option that provides sensate glabrous skin and durable coverage for selected distal defects.

Case Report: We present the case of a 25-year-old male patient with a transverse right thumb tip injury classified as Allen type III, secondary to an avulsion mechanism, with a 1.5 × 2.0 cm defect and distal bone exposure. Reconstruction was performed using a Moberg flap, achieving complete defect coverage without additional bone shortening. Postoperative management included early mobilization and a progressive rehabilitation protocol.

Results: The flap demonstrated complete survival with adequate preservation of digital length and favorable clinical evolution. Follow-up revealed recovery of sensibility, preserved joint mobility, and progressive functional reintegration, with no evidence of necrosis, significant joint stiffness, or major complications.

Conclusion: The Moberg flap remains a reliable and effective reconstructive technique for Allen type III thumb tip injuries with bone exposure. Proper indication and meticulous surgical execution allow for satisfactory functional outcomes, reinforcing its role as a first-line option for distal thumb reconstruction.

KEYWORDS: Thumb tip injury; Allen classification; Moberg advancement flap; Volar neurovascular flap; Pulp defect

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INTRODUCTION

The thumb plays a fundamental role in hand function, contributing decisively to pinch, grasp, and fine manipulation. Injuries involving the thumb pulp, particularly those associated with soft tissue loss and bone exposure, represent a significant reconstructive challenge due to their direct impact on sensibility, stability, and manual dexterity.

The primary goals of thumb tip reconstruction include providing stable and durable coverage with glabrous skin, preserving digital length and contour, promoting sensory recovery—ideally through innervated tissue—and maintaining joint mobility while preventing contractures that may compromise interphalangeal and metacarpophalangeal joint function. Adherence to these reconstructive principles is essential to achieve satisfactory functional and aesthetic outcomes.

The Allen classification is a widely used system for categorizing distal fingertip and thumb injuries based on the level of tissue loss in relation to the nail bed and distal phalanx. It divides these injuries into four types, reflecting increasing severity from distal soft tissue involvement to more proximal tissue loss with bone exposure.

Allen type III injuries are characterized by transverse or oblique tissue loss involving the distal pulp and a significant portion of the nail bed, frequently associated with exposure of the distal phalanx. These injuries preserve the distal interphalangeal joint but present a reconstructive challenge due to the need for stable coverage, preservation of digital length, and restoration of protective sensibility. As a result, Allen type III lesions often require flap-based reconstruction rather than skin grafting, with sensate local flaps—such as the Moberg flap—being particularly well suited for achieving optimal functional and aesthetic outcomes. (Figure 1).

Within this context, the Moberg flap, described as a volar advancement flap based on both neurovascular bundles of the thumb, has become one of the most widely used reconstructive techniques for pulp defects. Its ability to provide sensate, well-vascularized glabrous skin with appropriate biomechanical properties distinguishes it from other local reconstructive options and skin grafts. It is generally indicated for small to medium-sized defects, typically up to 1–1.5 cm, with the possibility of extensions

or technical modifications in selected larger defects, given the inherent limitations of its advancement arc and the risk of excessive tension.

The aim of this article is to report a case of a transverse thumb tip injury with bone exposure classified as Allen type III treated with a Moberg flap, as well as to discuss its historical evolution, major technical modifications described in the literature, and relevant surgical and functional considerations for its appropriate clinical application.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 25-year-old right-handed male patient with no relevant comorbidities, including diabetes mellitus, smoking history, peripheral vascular disease, or neuropathy, was evaluated. The mechanism of injury consisted of an avulsion-type trauma to the right thumb, secondary to accidental traction caused by contact with a moving motorcycle chain. The injury occurred acutely and was characterized by soft tissue loss at the distal tip of the right thumb, accompanied by initial bleeding that was promptly controlled, localized pain, and absence of associated systemic symptoms.

I. Physical Examination: On focused physical examination of the hand, inspection revealed a transverse defect of the distal thumb pulp measuring approximately 1.5 × 2.0 cm, with loss of glabrous skin and subcutaneous tissue, as well as exposed distal phalanx bone. The wound margins were irregular, consistent with an avulsion mechanism, without evidence of gross contamination. The nail bed showed approximately 60% involvement, associated with avulsion of the nail plate. No signs of proximal tissue necrosis were identified, with only moderate localized edema observed.

Vascular assessment demonstrated preserved distal capillary refill of less than two seconds in the lateral remnants of the thumb, with appropriate skin temperature and coloration. Regarding mobility, the interphalangeal joint of the thumb exhibited active flexion and extension limited by pain, while the metacarpophalangeal joint was stable, without deviation, and showed decreased strength secondary to pain. Tendon examination confirmed functional integrity of the flexor pollicis longus, with active flexion against resistance, as well as intact extensor pollicis longus and brevis tendons.

Palpation revealed localized tenderness at the level of the distal phalanx without frank crepitus. Ligamentous stability of the metacarpophalangeal and interphalangeal joints was preserved, with no evidence of collateral instability. Examination of the second through fifth digits revealed no injuries, with full range of motion, adequate perfusion, and preserved sensation. The wrist showed no pain or functional limitation.

Imaging studies, including anteroposterior, lateral, and oblique radiographs of the thumb, confirmed distal phalanx bone exposure without evidence of proximal comminuted fracture or articular involvement.

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Based on clinical and radiographic findings, a diagnosis of transverse thumb tip injury with bone exposure, consistent with an Allen type III injury, and a 1.5 × 2.0 cm pulp defect secondary to an avulsion mechanism was established. Surgical management with coverage using a Moberg flap was indicated, considering the need to provide durable glabrous tissue, preserve digital length, and achieve functional benefit through a sensate flap based on the thumb neurovascular bundles, with the aim of optimizing both functional and aesthetic outcomes. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Preoperative images showing distal thumb injury classified as Allen type III.

II. SURGICAL TECHNIQUE

The procedure was performed under regional anesthesia using a digital block of the radial and ulnar neurovascular bundles of the thumb, with infiltration of 3cc of plain lidocaine per side. Following standard surgical preparation of the operative field with povidone-iodine solution, conservative debridement of devitalized tissues was performed, followed by meticulous hemostasis.

Once the wound bed was adequately prepared, minimal bony regularization of the distal phalanx was carried out using a rasp to obtain smooth bone edges, facilitating adequate defect coverage and preventing pressure points on the flap.

Flap design was achieved through midaxial incisions along the thumb, placed dorsal to the palmar neurovascular bundles and extending proximally from the distal edge of the defect. This approach allowed preservation of both neurovascular pedicles while maintaining the integrity of the glabrous pulp skin. The vascular supply of the thumb, provided primarily by the radial artery through its dorsal and palmar branches, is essential for maintaining tissue viability and serves as the anatomical basis for reliable neurovascular flap reconstruction. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Vascular supply of the thumb. RA - Radial Artery, SPBRA - Superficial Palmar Branch of Radial Artery, FPMA- First Palmar Metacarpal Artery, RIA - Radialis Indicis Artery, PPA - Princeps Pollicis Artery, UDA - Ulnar Digital Artery, RDA - Radial Digital Artery, SPA - Superficial Palmar Arch, DPA- Deep Palmar Arch.

Flap elevation was performed carefully in a plane superficial to the flexor pollicis longus tendon sheath, allowing sufficient tissue mobilization without compromising vascular supply. During this step, continuity of the flap with both neurovascular pedicles was maintained, and controlled release of the palmar fibrous septa limiting advancement was performed, always avoiding pedicle skeletonization. (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4. Marking and elevation of the Moberg flap

Figure 5. Elevation of the Moberg neurovascular flap.

The flap was then advanced distally to achieve complete coverage of the exposed bone. Fixation was performed using non-absorbable 4-0 nylon sutures in simple interrupted fashion, ensuring the absence of torsion or compression of the neurovascular pedicles. An appropriate nail splint was placed and secured using a figure-of-eight suture with 3-0 nylon. After release of ischemia, adequate flap perfusion was confirmed based on color, temperature, and distal capillary bleeding. (Figure 6)

Figure 6. Immediate postoperative appearance after flap fixation with slight flexion of the proximal interphalangeal joint.

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Donor site management consisted of primary closure, positioning the thumb in a controlled and temporary interphalangeal flexion to reduce tension on the flap and enhance viability. A soft compressive dressing and a short protective splint were applied to maintain flexion and protect the reconstruction during the immediate postoperative period.

Limb elevation was indicated for edema control, and a progressive rehabilitation protocol was initiated. Gradual active mobilization began at the fourth postoperative week, aiming to preserve interphalangeal and metacarpophalangeal joint mobility and initiate desensitization and sensory reeducation.

Regarding outcome variables, complete flap survival was documented, with no evidence of partial or total necrosis and adequate preservation of digital length relative to the extent of injury. During the follow-up for two weeks no infectious complications or need for reoperation were observed. (Figures 7 and 8)

Figure 7. Follow-up of the flap at 2 weeks post-surgery. Lateral projection

Figure 8. Follow-up of the flap at 2 weeks post-surgery.

DISCUSSION

Thumb tip injuries represent a particular reconstructive challenge due to the functional, sensory, and biomechanical relevance of the thumb, which contributes decisively to pinch, grasp, and fine manipulation. Pulp loss associated with bone exposure requires selection of a reconstructive technique capable of providing stable coverage, preserving digital length, and allowing recovery of protective sensibility—key factors for achieving satisfactory functional outcomes (1,2).

The Moberg flap, originally described in 1964 by Erik Moberg, marked a turning point in thumb pulp reconstruction by emphasizing the importance of sensibility in hand reconstructive surgery. This volar advancement flap,

based on both neurovascular bundles of the thumb, provides well-vascularized and innervated glabrous skin, distinguishing it from other local flaps and skin grafts, particularly in cases involving bone exposure (3–5).

Traditionally, the Moberg flap has been indicated for thumb pulp defects smaller than 1–1.5 cm, due to limitations in its advancement arc and the risk of excessive tension, marginal necrosis, or interphalangeal joint stiffness (6). However, multiple studies and clinical reports have demonstrated that, with meticulous surgical technique and specific modifications, its indications can be expanded to larger defects, especially in young patients without comorbidities and with adequate digital perfusion (7,8).

In the present case, the transverse 1.5 × 2.0 cm defect with bone exposure represented a borderline scenario for the classic Moberg flap indication. Nevertheless, preservation of the neurovascular pedicles, absence of associated tendon or joint injury, and the ability to perform conservative debridement without significant bone shortening allowed this technique to be used as the primary reconstructive option. Elevation of the flap in a plane superficial to the flexor pollicis longus sheath, together with careful release of the palmar fibrous septa, eased sufficient advancement without compromising distal perfusion, a critical factor for flap viability (4,6).

Over time, several modifications of the Moberg flap have been described to increase its reach and reduce closure tension. O'Brien introduced the concept of the neurovascular island flap, allowing greater mobility at the expense of additional proximal incisions and, in some cases, the need for skin grafting at the donor site (9). Subsequently, Dellon described proximal extension of the flap into the thenar eminence, increasing its advancement arc and expanding its indications for larger pulp defects (10). Other technical variants, such as V-Y advancement or Z-plasty closure, have been proposed to reduce tension and minimize postoperative stiffness (11).

Functional outcomes reported with the Moberg flap are generally favorable. Several clinical series report high flap survival rates, adequate preservation of digital length, and satisfactory recovery of protective sensibility, with functional two-point discrimination in most patients (6,7). Reported complications include interphalangeal joint stiffness, scar hypersensitivity, and partial flap necrosis, the latter typically associated with excessive tension or inadequate pedicle dissection (5,6).

Compared with other reconstructive options for thumb tip injuries with bone exposure—such as skin grafts, cross-finger flaps, or heterodigital flaps—the Moberg flap offers clear advantages in terms of sensibility, durability, and quality of the coverage tissue. Skin grafts are not suitable in the presence of bone exposure and lack mechanical resistance, while heterodigital flaps are associated with greater morbidity, prolonged immobilization, and, in many cases, inferior sensory outcomes (1,2,12).

CONCLUSIONS

The Moberg flap remains a valid, safe, reliable and effective reconstructive option for the management of transverse thumb tip injuries with bone exposure, when appropriately indicated based on comprehensive assessment of the defect and the patient, and executed with meticulous surgical technique, it allows satisfactory functional and aesthetic outcomes, even in borderline-sized defects such as the one presented in this report (6–8,10).

Its ability to provide sensate glabrous tissue, preserve digital length, and maintain satisfactory function positions it as a first-line reconstructive option compared with alternative techniques. (Table 1)

The present case demonstrates that even in borderline-sized defects, careful application of the Moberg flap—respecting anatomical principles and minimizing tension on the neurovascular pedicles—can achieve stable coverage, favorable clinical evolution, and satisfactory functional outcomes. Appropriate patient selection, meticulous surgical technique, and a structured immobilization and rehabilitation protocol are key determinants for optimizing results and minimizing complications.

This report reinforces the role of the Moberg flap as a fundamental tool within the reconstructive armamentarium of the plastic surgeon for distal thumb injuries, providing clinical evidence supporting its use in carefully indicated scenarios.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Gabriel Alcalá-Soto: conceptualization, project administration, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Luis Enrique Hernández-Alcalá:** formal analysis, resources, software, writing – review and editing. **Denisse Sánchez-Padilla:** investigation, methodology, resources. **Rodrigo Alonso Mata-Pérez:** investigation, resources. **Yuliet Guadalupe Sánchez-Javier:** investigation, resources. **Rafael Mendez-Reynosa:** investigation, resources. **Leslie Denisse Castillo-Campos:** investigation, methodology, resources. **Irad Antonio Zuñiga-Salazar:** investigation, resources. **Aranza Maleny Esquivel-Ramos:** investigation, resources. **Rocío Kinnereth Mateos-Rodríguez:** investigation, resources.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest related to this article.

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CONSENT

The patient provided written informed consent for the publication of this case report and any related images.

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Table 1. Comparative table of reconstructive techniques for digital tip injuries in the thumb

Reconstructive Technique	Main Indications	Advantages	Disadvantages / Limitations
Moberg flap (volar neurovascular advancement flap)	Transverse or oblique thumb pulp injuries with bone exposure; small to medium-sized defects ($\approx 1-1.5$ cm, expandable in selected cases)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides sensate glabrous skin Preserves thumb length and contour Excellent functional and sensory outcomes Local technique with no morbidity to other digits Considered the technique of choice for thumb pulp reconstruction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited advancement due to tension Risk of interphalangeal joint stiffness if early mobilization is not initiated Not ideal for large defects without technical modifications
Modified / extended Moberg flap	Slightly larger thumb pulp defects (>1.5 cm) with bone exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preserves the advantages of the classic Moberg flap Increased arc of advancement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased technical complexity Potential need for additional incisions or closure under tension
O'Brien-type neurovascular island flap	Large thumb pulp defects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greater flap mobility Preservation of sensibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May require skin grafting at the donor site Increased local morbidity Risk of contracture
Volar V-Y advancement flap	Small defects without significant bone exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple surgical technique Favorable aesthetic outcomes in small defects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited advancement Variable sensory recovery Not ideal in cases with significant bone exposure
Cross-finger flap	Large defects when local flap reconstruction is not feasible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliable soft tissue coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires a two-stage surgical procedure Prolonged immobilization Donor finger morbidity Inferior sensory outcomes
Heterodigital flaps	Extensive and complex injuries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides adequate volume and wide coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High morbidity Limited sensory results Technically more demanding procedure
Skin graft	Superficial defects without bone exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple procedure Rapid execution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contraindicated in the presence of bone exposure Poor mechanical resistance Inadequate sensory recovery
Bone shortening with primary closure	Very distal injuries in carefully selected patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast technique Avoids the need for flap reconstruction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loss of digital length Compromises thumb function and aesthetic outcome